

ARCTIC PASSION

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Report on missing elements for an improved
Arctic observing system

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**ARCTIC
PASSION**

Work package

WP 1: Establishing an adaptative and more complete Arctic observing system

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9 - Snowchange

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1. Introduction

This report is a part of the wider assessment of the missing elements in the Arctic regarding observations, spatial and temporal scales of change and multiple ways of knowing (scientific, Indigenous and local knowledge, see more in Johnson et al. 2015, 2016). The specific aim of this deliverable is to assess how “community-based monitoring (CBM) networks can expand observations, improve baselines, identify and monitor new indicators, local impacts and how CBMs can be sustained.”

The role and applications of community-based monitoring (CBM in short) have existed in the Arctic for decades. Proliferation of these systems that embrace, support and engage with the Indigenous communities and local observations happened as a result of the Indigenous land claims and other equity mechanisms in the North American Arctic.

For example, we can see this in the results of the Inuvialuit Final Agreement in 1984 which also fostered the collaborative management boards as a part of these Indigenous rights and management arrangements. Secondly, we can also trace this process back to the Mackenzie Pipeline Inquiry led by Justice Thomas Berger in 1970s in NWT, Canada that validated and enabled methods to engage with Indigenous knowledge in environmental assessments. The James Bay and Quebec Cree Final Agreements also were a part of the development of CBM structures.

In this Arctic PASSION work report we are aware of the established CBM mechanisms, many of which have been developed in the North American Arctic (see Johnson et al. 2015):

Through CBM initiatives, Arctic residents conduct or are involved in ongoing observing and monitoring activities. Arctic Indigenous peoples have been observing the environment for millennia, and CBM often incorporates traditional knowledge, which may be used independently from or in partnership with formal scientific monitoring methods.

Johnson et al. (2015) provide a range and differentiation of CBM systems: “Formal monitoring initiatives that define themselves as “community-based” use different approaches to community engagement. At one end of the spectrum, government or academic researchers or environmental organizations may enlist community members in collecting data or samples for initiatives driven by the information needs of institutions located outside the community. At the other end, residents and local institutions drive the establishment of monitoring initiatives based on information needs within the community. Within this range, community members may be involved in some or all aspects of the initiative, from setting goals and defining methods, to data collection, to analysis and interpretation, to sharing and disseminating the results and using them for decision making.”

Recent literature such as Gillette and Singleton (2002) looks at the main component of CBM – Indigenous and local knowledge, and argue that literature shows an erosion through engagements with western science. This is built on an understanding that the biggest gap in CBM work and associated dialogues between science and ILK systems do not address the

colonial past and present of hegemony of western science. This renders knowledge co-production and systemic integration even unreasonable according to them (2022).

For Arctic PASSION and the 2020s Arctic CBM-monitoring, we can determine based on the above framing that the twinning forces of accelerating change in natural ecosystems, climate and weather as well as further role of reliance on technologies is re-shaping the way Indigenous and local communities are observing the present. We have to be also aware of the past assumptions and problems associated with the CBM work and learn from them. Additionally, the war in Ukraine since February 2022 has altered the methods of inter-community exchanges for example under the Arctic Council and many other fora.

This report covers key messages from earlier EU Projects (Kepler, INTAROS, Section 2) that have looked at gaps in monitoring, reviews the operational areas of CBM work in Arctic PASSION (the Indigenous and local communities involved, Section 3) and offers summary conclusions for the aim of

- expanding observations
- improving baselines
- identifying and monitoring new indicators, local impacts
- and actions on how CBMs can be sustained further

2. Gap Analysis from INTAROS and KEPLER – Key Messages

The EU H2020 project INTAROS¹ made an assessment (Tjernström, M. et al., 2019) of the present Arctic observation capacity, with focus on in situ systems. Many existing Arctic observing systems, especially outside Europe, were not included in that assessment which is therefore biased towards the European Arctic. The KEPLER² EU H2020 project identified research capacity gaps that must be closed in order to improve Polar Region monitoring and forecasting capabilities.

In this section, the main findings and recommendations from the INTAROS and KEPLER summary reports (Wilkinson, J. et al., 2020, Gabarró, C. et al, 2021) are summarised in a condensed and lightly edited form. Please note that the authors of the present report have not introduced any updates, additions or corrections apart from this light editing.

2.1 Atmospheric observations

Atmospheric observations over the Arctic Ocean need special consideration and possibly a new paradigm. In the marine Arctic there are very few in situ near-surface atmospheric observations, no stationary observation system and very few in situ observations of atmospheric vertical structure.

The available atmospheric observations from the Arctic Ocean with the highest quality come from ship-borne scientific expeditions; however, these typically score low on data management issues in addition to, by definition, not being sustainable and are too sparse in time and space. Additionally, there is a strong seasonal bias to summer or early autumn, when ice conditions favour navigation.

The only type of observations with a very good coverage are satellite observations; however, the INTAROS assessments showed that the quality of the satellite observations over the Arctic is often insufficient for climate monitoring and environmental forecasting.

More routine observations by ships of opportunity would also be extremely useful as well as development of low-cost autonomous observation stations also for features like atmospheric vertical structure.

2.2 Ocean and sea-ice observations

The assessments show that the in situ ocean and sea ice observing systems have high sustainability when they are funded by national programmes over several decades. The most prominent programmes are the hydrography, ecosystem and fisheries monitoring programmes in the Barents, Greenland and Norwegian seas, the German FRAM programme with seafloor

¹ INTAROS: Integrated Arctic Observation System

² KEPLER: Key Environmental monitoring for Polar Latitudes and European Readiness

observatory, mooring arrays and hydrography sections in the Fram Strait, and the Norwegian Polar Institute's Fram Strait Arctic Outflow Observatory.

The International Arctic Buoy Program, the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring Programme and the tide gauge network around the Arctic are other examples of systems that have been operated since the 1990s. Ship-based observations are an essential part of ocean and sea ice observing system in the Arctic. Data collection from ships is done through regular monitoring programmes as well as through research cruises.

In the Arctic ice-covered areas, all the ship-based observations are taken from icebreakers. Most of these expeditions take place in the summer-autumn season, when year-round observing systems (moorings and ice buoys) are deployed and recovered. The lack of multidisciplinary (physical, biogeochemical and biological) data from the Arctic Ocean calls for development and implementation of complex, heavily-instrumented observing platforms, collecting autonomous observations of multiple variables collocated in space and time.

The deployment and operation of a network of such platforms can be done by coordination between the institutions operating ice-going vessels that are present in the Arctic every year. Development of observing systems should also target small, low-cost, long-endurance and mobile autonomous platforms that could be deployed during research expeditions and from ships of opportunity, particularly in the rarely accessed regions.

Observation from polar orbiting satellites is the only method by which consistent ocean and sea ice data can be obtained regularly for the whole pan-Arctic region. There are now operational observing systems organized through the Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS). These services provide regular data products as well as forecasting products for both sea ice and open ocean variables.

Satellite passive microwave observations of sea ice concentration represent the longest and most mature system for sea ice monitoring, covering more than 40 years of daily observations. In the last decade also ice thickness is retrieved from satellite altimeters. In open ocean areas, satellite observing systems for seas surface wind, waves and temperature as well as sea level and ocean colour have been developed and provide regular data products that are distributed through the CMEMS services.

2.3 Terrestrial Arctic

Atmospheric observations over Arctic land suffer partly from lack of spatial coverage and uneven data quality. INTAROS results show that while a better spatial coverage would be beneficial, especially for monitoring of trace gases and aerosols, over large areas and at least for the sounding and surface observation network GOS, an improvement of the quality of observation and more reference stations would be more important than increasing the network density.

Land surface observing requires a balance between space-borne and in situ observing systems. The land surface is very heterogeneous and it is difficult to cover sufficiently with in situ observations, but the available satellite observations require development to enhance the

quality of the information. In this respect, supersites are crucial in providing co-located measurements of a large number of terrestrial and atmospheric variables, that together enable the testing and development of model and algorithms for satellite retrievals and for the assimilation of the satellite data into operational models.

There are perhaps less than 20 supersites in the Arctic (mainly belonging to the IASOA, GEM and SIOS networks), most of which were not included in the INTAROS assessment because INTAROS partners were not directly involved in the measurements (particularly for sites in Canada, Alaska, Svalbard, and Russia).

Observations of snow properties would benefit greatly from coordination with other land-based observing system, e.g. the WMO/GOS network of weather observations and the quality of observations from land-based observatories could be greatly enhanced by a coordination of instruments and calibrations, especially in Russia.

In situ observations of glacier and ice sheet mass balance in the Arctic are crucial to validate regional climate models and satellite-derived data products, yet have issues with sustainability. Observational networks on glaciers and ice sheets are notoriously difficult to maintain and often entail costly logistical support. Most such efforts have started out as research projects, expanded and maintained, sometimes over decades, by time-limited project funding. Similarly, the in situ land-ice monitoring datasets acquired need to reach a higher level of maturity in terms of data access and uncertainty characterization. Most of the land-based and ice-based stations have low maturity in metadata and data uncertainty handling.

One of the weakest aspects of terrestrial satellite products is the lack of uncertainty characterization. Satellite remote sensing is the only viable method to gain complete coverage of land snow and ice in the Arctic, but satellite products rely heavily on relatively sparse in situ monitoring effort for validation, calibration, and uncertainty characterization.

Understanding land ice contribution to sea level rise, the changes in seasonal snow and permafrost conditions, there is a need for both deploying dedicated satellite missions and to strengthen and sustain the in situ component that these missions depend on.

2.4 Community-based monitoring and Citizen Science

The INTAROS assessment states that Community-based environment monitoring (CBM) programs can complement scientist-led observing programmes. CBM is characterized by:

1. use of different and often simple methodologies with low costs;
2. engagement of indigenous knowledge holders and other long-term residents with substantial environmental knowledge (Tengö et al. 2021), and;
3. large sample size or high density, area and time (Danielsen et al. 2018). At least in some disciplines, scientists have started to incorporate CBM programmes and CBM tools into their work because they have found that their science has improved (e.g., Mercer et al. 2010; Eerkes-Medrano et al. 2017).

Monitoring conducted by and anchored in communities is likely to gain in importance where scientist-based monitoring is sparse, and for environmental attributes where remote sensing cannot provide credible data (Danielsen et al. 2021).

The KEPLER report states that community-based and local monitoring programmes offer a strong potential for linking environmental to awareness raising and enhanced decision making at all levels of management. Community-based programmes could provide important information, feedback and in situ data that potentially could fill the gaps and contribute in climate modelling and in research within such areas as risk management, safety, food- and water security.

Community-based programmes can also be a way to fulfil the rights of the citizens to take part in decisions that are related to their regional and local areas and to be able to take part in knowledge sharing in order to develop and safeguard their environment.

KEPLER also recommends to “develop mechanisms to encourage, support and facilitate more Citizen Science³ projects to be involved in the calibration and validation (“Cal/Val”) of the present and future Copernicus products and services.”

Recommendations from INTAROS

Based on the above assessments, INTAROS drew up a list of key recommendations for sustainable Arctic observing systems for the application areas addressed in the assessment:

- 1. Observing systems are most sustainable when they are part of monitoring programmes with long-term funding from national, international or regional organisations** such as Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme under Arctic Council, EU infrastructure programmes or the Copernicus programme. The in situ component of the observing systems is often based on national and international research projects with short-term funding and has therefore lower sustainability. The in situ component needs an improved funding model to be sustainable.
- 2. There is an urgent need to improve the coordination between the operational monitoring systems and the research-funded observations.** Collaboration between national meteorological, oceanographic and other operational agencies and Arctic research programmes should increase.
- 3. Existing infrastructures should be better utilized to achieve more cost-effective Arctic in situ observing across multiple disciplines.** The infrastructures consist of observation stations including supersites, ships and icebreakers, drifting platforms, underwater installations and aircraft. Icebreakers can be used to increase atmospheric, ice-ocean and seafloor observations in most of the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.
- 4. The largest gaps in the observing systems are found in the marine ice-covered parts of the Arctic, where deployment of new autonomous observing platforms is of high priority.**

³ Citizen Science (CS), defined in the KEPLER report as: “Voluntary collaborations in scientific research that is conducted, in whole or in part, by non-professional scientists, whose outcomes both advances scientific knowledge, and increases the public’s understanding of science.”

The platforms should provide long-term monitoring of physical, biogeochemical and biological variables. This requires development of new sensors and robust and cost-effective platforms as well as ice-going vessels for deployment and maintenance of autonomous platforms and for observations that need involvement of personnel.

5. **Terrestrial in situ observing systems should focus on upgrading and enhancing existing stations, including improvement of instrument technologies and development of new autonomous instruments.** Arctic supersites, which are stations with extensive multidisciplinary measurement capacity should be enhanced. Supersite observations are critical to provide high-quality ground truth data for validation of a number of satellite products as well as for numerical models and forecasting systems, such as those under the Copernicus services.
6. **While there are significant investments in satellite observing systems, through Copernicus and other satellite programmes, the INTAROS assessment showed that the quality of some satellite data is not adequate.** Moreover, there is also a lack of uncertainty characterization of satellite data, which restricts their usefulness in data assimilation. In the marine Arctic, satellite observations, ship-based scientific observations, data assimilation and model reanalysis must be considered as integrated parts of the system, where each has an important role. This will require substantial and coordinated improvements in all three areas; satellite and in situ observing, data assimilation and numerical models.
7. **The generally low scores on data handling from in situ field programs remain a problem,** given some of the recommendations above. The assessment concludes that this is a consequence of how these programs are funded and is intimately linked program sustainability and the funding model for scientific projects.
8. **Arctic observing systems also include Community-Based Monitoring (CBM) systems** established by local communities in a bottom-up process.

KEPLER recommends to prioritise in situ measurements for calibration and validation of the remote sensing data in the Polar Regions, to reduce the identified uncertainties associated with Copernicus remote sensing and models output polar products. By developing a framework whereby Copernicus services can better utilize European polar research assets (i.e. stations, ships, aircrafts, and people) to provide needed calibration and validation opportunities for Copernicus Services products.

KEPLER also lists specific parameters that could be acquired with new satellites:

- Floating ice: Sea ice type, Iceberg detection, Ice extent, fraction and concentration, Sea ice (iceberg) drift, Sea ice thickness, Surface temperature, Snow depth
- Glaciers and ice caps: Surface velocity, Extent, Mass balance
- Ice sheets: Grounding lines, Surface velocity, Extent/Calving front, Surface melt extern, Mass change
- Snow on land: Snow water equivalent, Extent Fraction

Furthermore, KEPLER provided specific recommendations on synergetic parameters (produced by combining data from satellite instruments operated in different modes), such as phytoplankton groups and soil moisture.

The KEPLER report additionally lists recommendations for assimilation of different parameters in models, but we consider model improvements as such to be beyond the scope of the present recommendation report focussing on missing elements for an improved Arctic observing system and do not refer to them in any detail here. We note, however, that that in Arctic PASSION's WP3 there will be efforts on the usage of model frameworks (including assimilation) in shaping an observing network for specific use cases. These results also will have implications regarding the usefulness of different observational datasets for assimilation.

There remain significant roadblocks, including data processing, in terms of Copernicus' ability to deliver information near-real time (NRT) to support critical operations such as disaster management and search-and-rescue.

3. Addressing and Assessing Divergence in CBM Observations Across the Arctic Regions

In this section, we assess some of the specific divergence and gaps in methods in the Arctic CBM networks, learning from INTAROS and KEPLER as well as from literature (Johnson et al. 2015, 2016, Mustonen and Van Dam 2021 amongst others) derived from the Arctic PASSION member Indigenous communities (Alaska, Canada, Greenland, Sámi communities and pre-war, Siberian Indigenous communities):

3.1 Aspects of Alaskan Indigenous Knowledge

The Indigenous community of Unalakleet, Alaska, is located on the Norton Sound, Bering Sea, in Western Alaska. It is the home of Yupiaq and Iñupiaq peoples. Residents of Unalakleet have participated in framing and sharing of CBM observations for over 20 years. Mustonen and Van Dam (2021) report that:

The urgent situation in this region did not begin with recent events; rather, the drivers started generations prior, beginning with colonization and including a long history of injustice in Alaska... As Burch (2012) demonstrates, from our focus location of Unalakleet on the Norton Sound and North all the way to Utqiagvik was a region actually governed, owned and administered by Iñupiaq peoples belonging to distinct Nations with key territories, borders, customary law and inherent social structures... For larger society, the understanding of climate and associated environmental change can be reformed to correct *how* we know things and *why* things are understood as they are.

Mustonen and Van Dam (2021) use the example of the Indigenous knowledge from Elder Stanton Katchatag, from Unalakleet, who was able to observe marine temperature shifts starting already in 1970s:

“I think the warming of uh, the weather, is becoming noticeable about twenty-five to thirty years, it’s slow, you know. But when I think back, that’s about the time when it seems like it changed.”

This oral history co-researching event happened in August 2002. His observation would position the initial start of the change into 1972 (‘thirty years ago’). The indicators he was observing were the temperature and the changes in sea currents. Linking this with science observations they show a clear increasing trend; the annual-averaged air temperature increased by a rate of nearly +0.5 °C per decade since 1970, approximated using a linear least-squares fit.

Mustonen and Van Dam (2021) conclude their assessment:

“We know from the village of Unalakleet and national sources that Elder Katchatag was a highly-respected knowledge holder who keenly observed his home waters and surrounding terrestrial ecosystems. Born in 1917, at the beginning of the co-researching in August 2002 he was 85. As Macdonald (2000) shows, Inuit and Iñupiaq Elders do not share their personalized key knowledge unless they feel that it is important for the community, for the present situation, or for other weighing circumstances. Elder Katchatag stressed that a change that *he*

perceived and *judged* to be relevant to discuss had started in 1972. Two key indicators for the Norton Sound and Bering Sea – currents and temperature – were out of place in his world. Whilst Elder Katchatag did not convey what it means exactly, he decided to put the main meaning in the oral history into the accepting of an anomaly. We can assume that Unalakleet hunters, fishermen and other community members had established their own criteria for ‘stable conditions’ or ‘change within a normal’ during the time they had been living in the village and on the coast. Equally so we may assume that Elder Katchatag had grown to form his standards of ‘normality’ since 1917 and the early 1920s when he started to practice subsistence and later commercial harvests on the North Bering Sea.”

3.2 Canadian Indigenous Knowledge (with contributions from Sabrina Heerema, Arctic Passion)

Here we can highlight the extensive work of Leslie McCartney who has been living with the Gwich'in people in NWT, Canada and working with them on their oral histories. This provides, as identified in Johnson et al. (2015) reflections from the North American context, applicable in Arctic Passion.

Leslie lived in Tsiigehtshik for three years in the early 2000s and has worked with the Gwich'in since 1998 when the Gwich'in Social and Cultural Institute (GSCI) asked McCartney—who was then a postgraduate (and mature student) at Trent University in Ontario, Canada, working on her master's degree in cultural anthropology—to be the project coordinator in the Gwich'in Elders' Biographies Research Project, a project to record the life stories of Gwich'in Elders.

She was asked to interview and record the stories of twenty-three of the oldest Elders in the four NWT Gwich'in communities (Fort McPherson, Aklavik, Inuvik, and Tsiigehtchic). Most of the Elders interviewed are members of the last generation to fluently speak *Dinjii Zhu' Ginjik*, the Gwich'in language, as their mother tongue. *Dinjii Zhu' Ginjik* is one of the most endangered Indigenous languages in Canada and it is the most endangered Dene (Athapaskan) language in the Northwest Territories.

The land is central to the Elders' narratives. Because the Gwich'in 'live off the land' through seasonal access of the resources that land and water provide, the Elders' stories often mention the names of places they travelled to and lived on. While some place names describe geographical features; others are related to the resources that can be found there.

Many said that when talking about the land, they wanted to speak in Gwich'in because their language was more descriptive and they could discuss the land better in their own language. Land is so integral to the Gwich'in lifestyle that the various band names reflect the landscape on which they lived. For example, *Gwichya Gwich'in* literally means “people of the flat lands” (Gwichya = “flat land”; Gwich'in = “people”).

This name is given to the people who live in the Mackenzie River area where the land is flat. The name refers to the entire lowland region around the confluence of Tsiigehnjik and Nagwichoonjik (Arctic Red River and Mackenzie River). The people living around the Fort McPherson area call themselves the *Teet?it* Gwich'in. *Teet?it* refers to the headwaters of *Teet?it Gwinjik* (the Peel River), their traditional homeland prior to the arrival of the fur trade.

Through reading Indigenous oral histories, it is possible to learn more about the place names, history and culture of the Gwich'in. Elders play crucial roles as teachers of traditional knowledge, history, language, and culture; a way of life based on a special spiritual relationship between the Gwich'in and the land; the preservation and respect for the land as essential to the well-being and subsistence lifestyle of the Gwich'in people and their culture. Through this cooperation with the Gwich'in we also hope to increase respect and understanding of the culture.

While scientific data is regarded as authoritative, Indigenous knowledge can be viewed as an alternative, less-reliable source and there is scepticism about its usefulness. However, Indigenous and local knowledge is accurate knowledge that has been preserved and passed down through generations, and not only through generations but since the world was created.

As the first item in the preamble of the Gwich'in Comprehensive Land Claim Agreement acknowledges, *“the Gwich'in have traditionally used and occupied lands in the Northwest Territories and in the Yukon from time immemorial.”* In addition to supplementing gaps in scientific knowledge, oral history (stories) are ways of talking about the past and hearing voices that have been, to date, marginalized. They are central in expanding the depth and scales (INTAROS, Johnson et al. 2016) of CBM observations.

1.3 Greenlandic “User Knowledge”

Kalaallit Nunaat, Greenland, is the home of Inuit peoples. Arctic PASSION focuses on the Attu and Aasiaat communities as well as the NW Greenlandic communities. The Greenlandic law of 1999 established the role of “user knowledge” as a basis of community-based observations, but does not explicitly acknowledge Indigenous knowledge.

The PISUNA project (www.pisuna.org) has established mechanisms for engaging with the communities on their observations. Arctic PASSION will continue this process by supporting those elements which are missing from the 1999 User Knowledge Law, including

- species seasonal extent and observations
- linguistic biocultural information
- women’s knowledge
- back casting environmental change especially regarding Davis Inlet

For this work report, Danielsen (2022) provided an update of the post-INTAROS context in the PISUNA work that has taken place. According to him the central role of the Greenlandic municipalities and institutes in Nuuk remains high in terms of linking observations with decision making and maintaining observational networks.

He identified the high staff turn and administrative changes in Greenland over in recent years as a hindrance to the stable observational flow from the communities to the authorities. New organisations like Oceans North Canada have arrived in Greenland and are also involved in monitoring activities. Links to the Nunavut Wildlife Board in Canada have also strengthened.

Danielsen (2022) identified needs that could be undertaken with Arctic PASSION, including a searchable database of observations under PISUNA, expanding the work to all of Greenland, and producing high-end maps to show status and trends of change over time and space. Lastly, he stressed the need to link natural resources decision making with the local observations and used the example of the Greenlandic halibut as a potential first case that could be advanced.

1.4 Sámi Community Knowledge, Including Gendered Ways of Knowing

Sámi Indigenous knowledge is a living process of engaging with the Sápmi, the Sámi homeland. Central to the observations of Sámi are the iconic traditional trades of hunting, reindeer herding, fishing and gathering. Most of the Sámi CBM observations have not been gathered ever in a systematic way, partly due to the lack of rights to lands and waters and early implementation of the CBM approach in Sápmi.

Brattland and Mustonen (2018) summarize their findings in a recent table: *“Comparing knowledge production involving traditional knowledge across examples”* which offers indicators on engagement with Indigenous knowledge, observations and decision making nationally which builds on the need recognized by Johnson et al. (2016) and Danielsen (2022) in linking governance with observations:

Criteria	Kolarctic project	Joint working group	Näätämö
Context, goal and method	Scale sample research project on genetic distribution of salmon stocks in fishers’ catches to arrive at new knowledge on mixed-stock harvest in northern Norway	Working group set down by the Norwegian Environment Agency to arrive at new policy on salmon regulations in northern Norway	Co-management project between Skolt Sámi and Snowchange to contribute to restoration of Näätämö catchment area
Outcomes in terms of salmon sustainability	Discovery of high proportion of Russian salmon in regional catches	None.	Restoration of river, discovery of invasive species, establishment of a working community observation network, self-imposed quotas per families, detection of expansion of pike

Stakeholder position (Sámi rights holder and or/knowledge holder)	Sea-based salmon fishers participating as stakeholders and private rights holders	Fishers and Sámi organisations as stakeholders in management	Fishers and villages enjoying special Skolt Sámi rights
Knowledge production model:	Integration and validation	Parallel approach	Co-production
Diversity of actors involved	Salmon biologists, salmon fishers, Finnmark County Governor	Salmon fisher organisations, Sámi Parliament, Norwegian Environment Agency	Snowchange, Saa'mi Nu'ett cultural organisation, fishers, Indigenous knowledge experts, teams of scientists
Salience (relevant for the needs of policy makers)	Directly relevant	Not very relevant	Partly relevant
Legitimacy:	Low	High	High
Level of participation of Sámi/local actors	Fishers participation in data collection	Fishers' organisations participation in joint working group with management body and Sámi Parliament	Specific Sámi participation at all levels from data collection to control of project
Acceptance of application among indigenous groups (social robustness)	Varying, depending on regional outcome and benefits to fishers	Not at all	High
Credibility	High	Low	High
Influence on policy	Direct implications. Results on genetic patterns in the mixed-stock fishery accepted among policy makers and most fishers	Negative implications. Discontinuation of dialogue between authorities, fishers and Sámi Parliament	Few implications. High local and international acceptance, the method beginning to be accepted among regional and national policy makers

(adapted from Brattland and Mustonen 2018).

Brattland and Mustonen (2018) summarize their assessment by saying:

“there are already ongoing relations between scientists and local people in terms of collecting data (Kolarctic Salmon project) and monitoring salmon habitats (Näätämö), which does provide the impetus for healthy salmon co-management in both Norway and Finland. This leads us to a new and perhaps the most important realisation from this inquiry. The absence of international TEK and ILK definitions in some local and regional contexts has allowed for example the Skolt Sámi to carve their own spaces and interpretations for the rather general terms of Indigenous and local knowledge and practice. While this has produced scientifically relevant observations of arrival species (Mustonen, 2015) or ecological restoration (Apgar et al., 2016), these undefined spaces and contexts are extremely relevant for the regional discussions on ILK. The risks associated in embracing the ‘un-bound’ and diverse knowledges of Sápmi should thus be reflected against the unity of TEK definitions and their locations inside the national and international contexts in the future. Building on the evidence from the existing monitoring and co-management processes, we encourage rethinking what a policy-relevant Arctic knowledge co-production process should look like. This might mean giving up on the idea of traditional knowledge as a system of knowledge comparable to science, in order to achieve the most salient results, and in the end socially robust knowledge. In the case of the Näätämö project, we believe that part of the reason for the success of the Näätämö project is exactly the complementary co-production approach, the status of a Sámi collective as rights holders, and its lack of definition of TEK as a system or body of knowledge which allowed for the participants’ Skolt Sámi knowledge to influence the research. It has transformed the Skolt Sámi from victims of climate change impacts into agents of transformation restoring habitats to increase salmon resilience in less than a decade. Although lacking official recognition, a remarkable path of success emerges, if all parties have willingness to share, explore and implement in new ways for the improvement of nature and people.”

Pauliina Feodoroff (2021), Sámi leader who is also working on the Arctic PASSION CBM issues has written a very powerful link between gendered ways of knowing and the observations, that summarizes many of the gaps identified by Brattland and Mustonen (2018):

I have noticed that many Sámi women of my generation - who have been born in the intersecting moment of an interrupted traditional world and a transfer into the modern world - have found ourselves, in different scales, working either in defending our waters or our land.

We are being guided by the pain that we feel in our bodies.

Our bodies act as gauges of environmental change: the first indicators and first responders of something happening.

I lead catchment-wide ecological restoration work in Näätämöjoki river in the Sámi home area in Finland.

It is based on the knowledge and observations of human-induced change by our traditional fishermen and reindeer herders.

Indigenous knowledge and Western Science offer us concepts and possibilities to reflect on those changes that the waters in our bodies have known and reminded us of what has happened already much earlier. Changes in temperature, pain and the gradual passing of pain, waves, and intrusions within our bodies are knowledges that are difficult to communicate.

It seems that especially women are more sensitive to receiving messages from their home environments. And, thus, our Indigenous conservation work ends up being no longer a choice but a bodily commitment.

This realisation raises a lot of difficult questions of what or who controls our bodies, especially in this modern space of broken traditions.

Indigenous waters and lands strive to be well and prosper just like our human communities.

3.5 Special Role of Nomadic Communities in Siberia: *Role of Linguistic Knowledge in Arctic Observations and Place Names*

The Russian Arctic is the largest terrestrial part of the Arctic and also has the longest marine coastal territories. Before the war starting in February 2022 the region was connected with the Arctic collaborations, but these have since been stopped.

However some examples of early CBM networks have been established in the vast region (see Evenki Atlas 2020). We can determine a few of the key critically important features of the Siberian Indigenous CBM systems in summary form to be addressed:

- Many of the Indigenous communities in Siberia, such as the Nenets and the Chukchi maintain *nomadic* lifestyles that traverse multiple ecozones (from taiga in winter to tundra in spring and summer) of reindeer herding – they observe vast territories of rapid change – permafrost events, species on the move, greening of the tundra etc
- Indigenous communities in Siberia are the last nomads and therefore the quality, core elements and observational interpretations of these communities should be seen as explicit and special – they represent in themselves a fragile and unique ways of knowing and remembering that should be recognized.
- Place names in the Indigenous languages represent extremely relevant mnemonic pegs in landscapes that offer significant opportunities for back casting and understanding past ecological change.
- Oral histories and Indigenous knowledge from Siberian Indigenous communities represent unique examples of Indigenous observations provided communities and knowledge holders have had a way of free, prior, informed consenting, represent a gap that should be filled in CBM networks in culturally appropriate ways. (summarized from Evenki Atlas, 2020).

4. Addressing the Gaps: Central Priorities

We have seen from the regional examples that the Arctic Indigenous communities and various levels of engagement with CBM come in many divergent ways – from rather well established in the Alaskan and Canadian Arctic, into legal context in Greenland that is in general rather specific, and then into the undefined spaces of cultural, gendered and nomadic knowledges and CBM potentials in Sámi and Siberian communities.

Johnson et al. (2015) summarized some key elements of addressing gaps in CBM work that are central also to the future of CBM networks – in summary some of the key issues according to them are:

- A. **Robust community engagement** is a key factor in the long-term viability of CBM initiatives.
- B. **Depending on the aims of the initiative, CBM data collection methods can use quantitative or qualitative approaches, or both.** Methods may include scientific field research, photos, journals, drawing, focus groups, and interviews. CBM that draws on TK typically involves eliciting and recording the observations and knowledge of community-identified experts through interviews, oral histories, and documentation of place names. Many communities are working to develop their own oral history archive.
- C. **Many Arctic CBM initiatives adapt technologies so they are easy to use, can reliably capture data in a cold environment, and will record data in a way that is responsive to local ways of interacting with the environment.** Projects have successfully adapted and integrated field computers and Global Positioning System (GPS) units, meteorological equipment, sea ice monitoring tools, and other technologies. Some initiatives use existing maps, often generated through Geographic Information Systems (GIS), to identify potential conflicts between industry and Indigenous uses of traditional territory.
- D. **Indigenous views have sometimes been critical of the role of technology in monitoring initiatives,** particularly in monitoring animal populations: both Inuit and Sámi have raised concerns about some techniques used in wildlife monitoring and the impacts of certain technologies such as radio collars for bear monitoring.

(summarized from Johnson et al. 2015)

Lastly as Brattland and Mustonen (2018) write we often find the CBM processes to be dismissive of the Indigenous and cultural interpretations of change, as we can see from the example above with Elder Stanton Katchatag from Unalakleet. Johnson et al. (2015) summarize some elements of how observations are linked in the larger frames of community life and how the co-interpretation, including welcoming divergent views (see Mustonen and Van Dam 2021), may lead to significant and novel discoveries of change:

- Within communities, informal monitoring and observing play a significant role in daily life, providing information that is critical to safe travel and successful hunting and harvesting activities. In these approaches, analysis is also conducted informally as community members process what they have observed by discussing their observations with others.

- More formal monitoring initiatives require a thoughtful approach to planning how different kinds of knowledge can be involved in different stages of a project, including the data analysis phase. Efforts to identify methods for linking Indigenous and scientific knowledge production approaches should be a priority of future work in this field.
- Ethics protocols have been developed to guide research practices in and with Indigenous communities in a number of contexts. These protocols include guidelines specific to particular Indigenous groups within a single nation state, such as those created by and for Canadian Inuit communities.
- Research suggests that higher levels of community engagement in monitoring lead to use of the information in local environmental management and decision making.
- CBM programs that participate in larger networks have the benefit of sharing information that is of local interest (community-to-community sharing). By linking to other monitoring and scientific research initiatives, community members gain a sense of being part of a wider collective. They also gain access to new ideas and resources that can improve techniques and lead to new discoveries. Being part of a larger network can therefore help sustain energy, interest, and excitement at the community level.
- **Most significantly, Johnson et al. (2015) stress that in its current state, CBM is not yet used up to its full potential.** Significant work remains to build networks among initiatives, build capacity for CBM in communities and regions where it remains underdeveloped, refine methods, and develop protocols for sharing data more widely. Investment and support are needed for developing new tools (e.g., for data management), training local residents to implement monitoring programs and interpret their results, and creating opportunities to exchange best practices, new research, and innovations in this field. Each of these elements will require robust, sustained funding and committed engagement from the Arctic observing community. An important first step is to identify relevant institutions and organizations interested in CBM and to develop stronger linkages among them that will facilitate networking and outreach.”

5. Conclusions on identifying missing pieces needed to establish the pan-AOSS and overcome current fragmentation – Key Early Messages

In conclusion building on these existing experiences of CBM work, we can see that establishing a unified CBM network is rather difficult. This is due to the unique biocultural, linguistic, social and ecological conditions across the north, and marine-terrestrial-nomadic-freshwater- and other nodes of observations.

Johnson et al. (2016) in their extensive review of mid-2010s CBM networks in the Arctic were able to determine some key questions that are parts of the solution space in CBM work. According to them good CBM work builds capacity or requires it in order to succeed – i.e. we need people and resources who are committed to and agree with the monitoring aims.

Recognising IK and TEK is still in its infancy in European North, and varying in practices in North America, albeit better established. Diversity of situations, contexts and scales is needed, according to Johnson et al. (2016). Technological adaptations can happen, but require appreciation of the local context, as was evident in the KEPLER determinations for remote areas in Murmansk region, Russia and Finnish Lapland.

Johnson et al. (2016) also note, that the incentive and role of links to natural resources governance plays a role, as well as a need to establish data management processes linked with sustaining the CBM networks over long time and spatial scales.

This work report includes overviews of the past activities in monitoring, including a short review of the KEPLER and INTAROS projects' assessments, Arctic PASSION Indigenous home areas participating in the CBM work and lastly, key literature and learned lessons in the CBM field. As we move to overcome present fragmented field and build a pan-Arctic observational system, we can in conclusion determine that in order to move forwards thematically and in ways of addressing the gaps in monitoring we should

- **embrace and explore more community-based observations of change that have been produced by co-researchers** understanding the cultural and community context as well as baselines of change currently outside the established monitoring, including smaller seismic events, past extreme weather and species migrations
- **implement Free, Prior, Informed Consent**, intellectual property rights and ownership of observations to be shared with CBM networks to increase the validity and security of Indigenous co-researchers
- **explore backcasting** from existing records, place names, gendered ways of knowing in consented manner
- **for the whole Arctic monitoring effort, establish streams of highlighting “significant change”** as interpreted and prioritized by the CBM co-researchers – these triggers of change can lead us to determine meaning and prioritization as well as further exploration that will then complement and dialogue with scientific observations and improve inter-operability of Arctic observations – however, these observations need to

follow the consented and respectful engagement with the local and Indigenous communities

- **explore “Arctic Crashes”** (Krupnik et al. 2020) as flashpoints of regime shifts and tipping points across the region and explore divergence and convergence from science and Indigenous knowledge.
- **fill instrument-based observation system shortcomings** in the marine, atmospheric, cryosphere and terrestrial domains, utilizing CBM, scientific in situ and remote sensing methods as appropriate

Arctic Passion over the next years will focus on advancing all of these gaps to the extent we can.

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